

The University of
Nottingham

TRAVESING BY RESECTION

Shwana Manguri

Department of Civil Engineering, The University of Nottingham, UK

Dissertation submitted to The University of Nottingham in partial fulfilment of the degree of Master of Science in [engineering surveying with geographical information science]

September 24, 2016

ABSTRACT

Every engineering surveying works require very precise and accurate measurement down to sub-millimetre. Considering this quality of measurements the highly developed survey instruments have been invented. In addition, there are numerous of measurements and adjustments methods have been proposed. The traversing is a very common method which is used to establish a high accurate control points and adjustment control networks. That is used where the control points are visible to each other, where there is enough space to setup instruments (Total Station), and where using GNSS (GPS) is available.

However, in the case of having invisible control points, limited space to setup instruments (Total Station), and where using GPS is restricted or limited, it is not possible to use any traverse methods and adjustments. In order to address this problem this dissertation is proposed and examined a new method which is traversing by resection.

For achieving the goal of the current dissertation ten trials have done with five main control stations. The data were collected within different observation that they are four, five, and six observations. Moreover, the tow different methods were used to calculate and analysis the data.

Finally, the results achieved from the dissertation are precise and accurate, which all the results are in the confident level that they are in the range of $\pm\sigma$ and $\pm 2\sigma$.

Keywords: [Traversing, Traverse Adjustment, Resection, Accurate, Precise, and Control Point]

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Firstly, I would like to thank God, for giving me the good health and strength to complete my final thesis. Undoubtedly this wouldn't be achieved without the enormous help from my supervisor. Therefore, I would like to express my special gratitude to Dr Martin Smith, for his encouragement and his support. I would like to extend my sincere thanks to all the academic staff at the University of Nottingham, especially in the Civil Engineering Department, for their effort of bringing new generation of engineers.

I wouldn't be here without the help from others, therefore, my sincere gratitude to everyone who has provided me with knowledge during my life, from the alphabet to what I have learned at the University of Nottingham.

I wish words could express my gratitude to my beloved parents, Mrwat and Braim, for their continuous support, and enduring this long period of my absence. I am also incredibly grateful to my beloved wife, Bayan, for her ongoing support, love and patience during the writing of my dissertation. I would like to extend my gratitude to my little daughter, Hasty, who was born during the writing of my dissertation and has brought me great joy. Moreover, I wish to extend my sincere thanks to my sisters and brothers, who tried to make up for my absence for the sake of my parents.

Last, but surely not least, thank you to the people of my country for supporting me and trusting me to complete my MSc programme, especially the Higher Committee of Educations in Iraq for supporting me financially during my studies abroad.

CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	2
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	3
LIST OF FIGURES	6
LIST OF TABLES	7
1. INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Overview	1
1.2 Problem Statement	2
1.3 Aim and Objectives.....	2
1.4 Research Methodology	2
1.5 Outline of the Dissertation	3
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	4
2.1 General Overview.....	4
2.2 Surveying Technology Review	5
2.3 An Overview of Total Station Development.....	6
2.4 Traverse Adjustment Methods.....	6
2.4.1 Compass Adjustment Method	7
2.4.2 Transit Adjustment Method.....	8
2.4.3 Tuttle’s Adjustment Method.....	8
2.4.4 Crandall Adjustment Method	10
2.4.5 Minimum Variance or Least Square Adjustment Method	11
2.5 Resection	11
2.5.1 Kaestner-Burkhardt Method.....	12
2.5.3 Cassini Method	13
2.5.4 Tienstra Method	14
2.5.6 Numerical Method for Solving Horizontal Resection.....	16
3. ASSESSMENT OF THE EXISTING METHODS	17
3.3 Assessments of Resection Methods.....	18
3.3.1 Kaestner-Burkhardt Method.....	18
3.3.2 Collins Method.....	19
3.3.3 Cassini Method	19
3.3.4 Tienstra Method	19
3.3.5 Method of Direct Distance-Based Positioning Without Redundancy	19
3.3.6 Numerical Method.....	19
4. NEW PROPOSED METHOD.....	20
4.1 Overview	20
4.2 The Proposed Method.....	20
4.2.1 Establishing Horizontal Coordinates From Observed Azimuths and Distances	21

4.2.2 Establishing Traverse Control Points by Resection	23
4.3 The Project Flow Diagram	29
CHAPTER 5: DATA MEASUREMENT AND ANALYSIS, AND ASSESSMENT OF THE NEW METHOD	31
5.1 Overview	31
5.2 The Field Description and the Used Instruments	31
5.3 Data Measurements	32
5.4 Data Analysis and Discussion	34
6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECCOMENDATIONS	43
6.1 Conclusions	43
6.2 Recommendations	44
REFERENCES	
APPENDICES	

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1, three point resection problem using Kaestner-Burkhardt method	Error!
Bookmark not defined.	
Figure 2, three point resection problems using the Collins method. Error! Bookmark not defined.	
Figure 3, three point resection problem as proposed by Cassini.....	14
Figure 4, (a) Three point resection problem using the Tienstra Method. (b) Basic geometry outlining the principles of the Tienstra Method	14
Figure 5, the direct distance-based positioning method (Easa, 2007)	15
Figure 6, three point resection Numerical Method (Dekov, 2012).....	16
Figure 7, Ideal sketch of data measurements and calculation steps	21
Figure 8, 8.a established horizontal coordinates, 8.b Polar coordinate analysis.....	21
Figure 9, 9.a Establishing Traverse Control Points by Resection, 9.b Collins Method	23
Figure 10, the observed directions and distances from resected point (RMIT University, 2005).	25
Figure 11, Methodology Diagram.....	29
Figure 12, Main entrance of Jubilee campus and three observed control points	31
Figure 13, Robotic Total Station TS60	32
Figure 14, standard graph for accuracy and precision (confident level graph).....	35
Figure 15, Confident level for easting misclosure of four observations measurements ..	36
Figure 16, Confident level for northing misclosure of four observations measurements.	36
Figure 17, Confident level for easting misclosure of five observations measurements...	37
Figure 18, Confident level for northing misclosure of five observations measurements .	37
Figure 19, Confident level for easting misclosure of six observations measurements	38
Figure 20, Confident level for northing misclosure of six observations measurements ..	38
Figure 21, different between Collin and least square method for easting misclosure of four observations measurements	39
Figure 22, different between Collin and least square method for northing misclosure of four observations measurements	39
Figure 23, different between Collin and least square method for easting misclosure of five observations measurements	40
Figure 24, different between Collin and least square method for northing misclosure of five observations measurements	40
Figure 25, different between Collin and least square method for easting misclosure of six observations measurements	41
Figure 26, different between Collin and least square method for northing misclosure of six observations measurements	41
Figure 27, Comparison between numbers of observation of the easting misclosures	42
Figure 28, Comparison between numbers of observation of the easting misclosures	42

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 3 with six observations	33
Table 2, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 3 with six observations	34
Table 3, results of four observation measurements of easting coordinates	34
Table 4, results of four observation measurements of northing coordinates	34
Table 5, results of five observation measurements of easting coordinates	34
Table 6, results of five observation measurements of northing coordinates	35
Table 7, results of six observation measurements of easting coordinates.....	35
Table 8, results of six observation measurements of northing coordinates	35

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview

Accuracy and precision have become one of the most important issues in the engineering surveying. The precision can be improved by iterating measurements. Also, accuracy can be obtained by closeness to the existing value. In the various engineering projects traversing adjustments has been applying to achieve as much as high level of accuracy. Thus, traverse can play a role as a control network surveys. When a new engineering construction project is to be made, the traverse system station must be established and surveyed in the area. As Gary in (2015) illustrated traverse survey are undertaken for many purposes:

- For the purpose of determining the positions of exiting boundary markers positions.
- For the purpose establishing the boundary lines positions.
- For the purpose of determining the boundary encompassed area.
- To select the positions of that points which data can be obtained for establishing different types of maps for instance, establish control for map making.
- Ground control point establishment for photographic mapping.
- For establishing control survey for collecting data related to the earthwork quantities in highway, utility, railroads, and other constructions work.
- For establishing control survey for locating highways, railroads, and other constructions work.

However, the technology has developed for example GPS still traversing is an efficient way to improve accuracy in the control network survey. Especially in those areas the GPS could not be applicable or where errors are effective especially reflection for instance; forest, underground, residential areas (cities) surveying and etc.

The Traversing consists of using a variety of instrument combinations to create polar vector in space, that is 'lines' with a magnitude (distance) and direction (bearing). These vectors are generally contiguous and create a polygon which conforms to various mathematical and geometrical rules. With the development of the instruments the methods of traversing have developed and the higher accuracy has provided. The equipment used generally consists of something to determine direction like a compass or theodolite, and something to determine distance like a tape or Electromagnetic Distance Meter (EDM).

In the last two centuries, the engineers and scientists have developed several methods for traversing adjustments. All of them are efficient and have different level of accuracy. For example, Compass adjustment method, Transit adjustment method, Tuttle's Adjustment Method (Tuttle, 1901), Crandall Adjustment Method (Crandall, 1914), and Crandall Adjustment Method (Sprinsky, 1987). All the traverse adjustment methods can be used in any situation if the area has enough space to setup instrument and visibility between control points. This dissertation suggested a new method for traversing when the control points are not visible to each other or in case of not having enough space to setup instruments like building edges. The suggested method named as traversing by resection.

Resection has defined in several different ways in the last century. The most significant and relevant definition is; resection is the technique of positioning a new control point by observing three or more control points from that point (Song et al. 2016). Moreover, there are two types of measurement have been conducting for resection networks; horizontal

directions (angles) and horizontal distances. The position named free station. The resection solutions are very which they include geometrical, graphical, numerical, and analytical methods.

This dissertation will examine the traversing by resection as a new method for traversing. Moreover, the accuracy of the suggested method going to be assessed, and the availability and workability of method going to be examined in the field. In addition, the literature of both of traversing and resection will be covered as literature review.

1.2 Problem Statement

1. Traversing can be undertaken in any areas where the control points are visible to each other. Where the control points are not visible to establish a new control point, the resection technique has to be applied.
2. In traversing work for establishing a new control point has to be has enough space to setup instrument. While, in many cases the area is restricted to setup instrument for example, in the forest, building edges, and crowd areas. Thus, resection going to be an alternative for establishing next control point.
3. In those areas using GPS restricted or limited due to high level of errors or lack of signals for instance, underground excavation, forest, and residential areas.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

The main purpose of this dissertation is to propose an accurate method for traversing. In addition, is to find errors (misclosure) for latitude and departure for all traverse nodes by resection method.

- From the field (study area) data were assembled.
- The performance of the existing methods and techniques in the literature was evaluated.
- New method was proposed based on the principles of the most accurate available resection methods in the literature.
- The new method is simulated based on the observations and interpretations of the assembled data.
- The performance of the new proposed method was assessed.

1.4 Research Methodology

1. The existing methods in the literature were reviewed to obtain a better understanding of the principles which the proposed method were based on.
2. Study area was selected and best-fit plan was proposed for taking measurements. Moreover, Total Station model was chosen depend on its accuracy and precision
3. The data from the field was measured based on various parameters as precision and accuracy.
4. The available methods in the literature were evaluated based on their performance and accuracy.
5. A new method was developed based on the concepts of the most accurate resection method. Ten trails have done to calibrate new method
6. The conclusions were made Based on literature review and current study.
7. Recommendations will be given for future research.

1.5 Outline of the Dissertation

This research project consists of six main chapters. Chapter one is an introduction about accuracy and precision, traversing, and surveying instruments. Moreover, this chapter provides the aims and objectives of this dissertation and methodologies to achieve the goal of the dissertation.

Chapter two is a reviewing of literature the past work of traversing and traverse adjustment methods. In addition, provides a literature of resection, and resection methods. The history of development of surveying instruments is a part of this chapter with considering the invention of the total station instrument.

The critical review of the existing models of both of traverse adjustments methods and resection methods are presented in chapter three.

On the other hand, chapter four is a detailed description about methodology and new proposed method with algorithm and mathematical steps to gain the project aims.

Chapter five presents data measurement and analysis, assessment of the proposed method.

Finally, in chapter six the main crucial conclusions are provided from the present project and a few important recommendations are presented as an extension of the project.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 General Overview

Total station instrument has integrated from an EDM that is the instrument of measuring direct distances, and an electronic theodolite that is the tool of measuring horizontal and zenith angles between the target and equipment. Total stations have available different types that they are designed for a variety of different precisions and applications requirements (ICSM, 2013). Total stations are predominantly undertaken the conventional traverse surveying technique, for establishing control networks. This instrument has been measuring a sequence of angles and distances for conducting a control survey that they are used to obtain the position of control marks. The total station type, auxiliary tools and surveying procedures all have a substantial effect on the survey observations (measurements) and thus the obtaining the position of survey control marks and uncertainties.

After inventing of electro-optical distance and angle measuring instruments, the high level of accuracy and the availability of digital computers brought about a widespread use of traverses in establishment of geodetic control points of various level of accuracy (Papo and Peled, 1977). The fundamental operation in surveying and the quality assessment in surveying is traversing and it is a skill which is all surveyors develops. These traverses have linear and angular misclosures that undertake within the satisfactory area are acceptable; which is possible to traverse adjustment observations to remove mathematical contradictions (Deakin, 2006). While these misclosures do not provide enough precision of the location of the traverse stations, although gross errors can be indicated by large misclosures and their analysis are required for sophisticated mathematical (Deakin, 2006).

These angles are read with a total station (theodolite) in a closed traverse, they usually have a small angular misclosure; if the amount of angular misclosure is not too larger and/or not larger than some particular amount it is usually spread out equally over all the observed angles. All the traverse azimuths are computed from an adopted or known azimuth of one of the lines. Consequently, these azimuths are contributing, with the observed distances, to compute departures and latitudes which algebraic sums for each of them is zero. However, in case of having any misclosure in latitudes and departures, this misclosure might be assigned to; all from errors of measuring length, or all from errors of measuring direction, or partly from errors of measuring length, partly from errors of measuring direction (Hornton-Smith, 1949).

All the above provided information is true for normal traversing methods because the rest of the points are measured subsequently in a step by step manner using an accurate devise. However, the proposed method is totally different from the conventional traverse methods because the rest of the points are not measured subsequently they measured in different techniques; firstly, observing distances and angles of several points from known point then resecting new control points subsequently till the close the traverse. These differences of the proposed method will bring accuracy and precision are computed differently, in the other word the method of adjustment will be different. This will be explained in the chapter four.

In this chapter surveying technology review and total station review will be discussed. In addition, the common traverse adjustment methods going to be explained. Moreover, resection methods which they are used in the proposed method will be demonstrated.

2.2 Surveying Technology Review

The technology has been advanced for surveying. This advancement has played an important role in progressing accuracy of measurement and alignment, but great advancing has happened in the last three decades. The state of surveying instruments evolution has described by Hodges et al., (1982). They addressed an Electronic Distance Measurement EDM device in 1968 like the WILD DI-10 made distance measurement easier. The WILD Tachymat TC-1 among the first instruments could store over 1800 block of data on one cassette (Hodges et al., 1982). The development of reduction size of recording device, and capability of store blocks which leads to increase recording data electronically and downloading observations. Deeth (1984) reported that now data loggers provide high capacity of storage to above about 800 surveyed points. About two decade later Bannister, Raymond and Baker (1998) also reported that the total station instrument last generation is the invention of removable memory card (PCMCIA). Its size is similar to the credit card, also it can slot into the total station which can store 10000 points and its store size is 1 Mb.. Nowadays, total station can be connected by the over 32 GB information on USB flash drive.

The scientists and Engineering surveying companies have been investigated to reduce the size and increase the storage capacity of surveying instruments. The Hodges et al., (1984) predicted that the automatic computation provided from the fully integrated system by combining electronic angle and distance, and incorporating micro processors, that was useful and logical development. The fully integrated system has protected the electronic measurement combine of both angle and distance, and microprocessor integrated which has able to automatic computation was the next logical advancement. Advantage of such instruments was introduced in the early of 1960's for measuring and recording data where funnel theodolite and total station developed. In 1977 at the XVFIG congress in Stockholm, introduced four total stations for measuring feature data which contain microprocessor to control the instrument for data processing (Hodges et al., 1984). This development continued by the end of 1980's total station developed and recognized as a single instrument which is has the ability to measure and record all field data automatically.

With the improvement in accuracy and speed by the surveying instruments, significantly the accuracy, productivity and speed of construction projects have increased. Pretorius et al., (1967) reported the high percentage of working cost is wage and salary, the cost of structure directly affected by lost every hour of productive work. Also, Hodges et al., (1984) showed the advantage of surveying tools, productivities were increased, errors were reduced, and more efficient use of resources. This improvement of surveying instruments has reduced the time consumption to data observation and calculation. Deeth (1984) has predicted the further improvement in surveying equipment are the man power reduction with reducing size, speed, and weight of measurement, also there are trial to invention the self-tracing instruments. Currently, the all prediction of Deeth can be seen.

Traditionally, the surface surveying distance measurement between points had done by stretching chain. Chain measurement for distance longer than chain length could take days or may be weeks to obtain sufficient accuracy. This hardness of measurement was leads to develop triangulation which was realized an effective way to reduce the base line length. (Hodges and Smith, 1982) observed that the great effective progressing has been made the application of close range electro-optical system of measuring distance. These difficulties were removed by the Electronic Distance Measurement EDM for measuring distance and elevation between two points. Hodges and Smith (1982) argued that the

most difficult part of surveying operation traditionally is the accuracy of distance measurement. The output of this development is trilateration and resection as a support to triangulation for the distance measurement accuracy. Hodges, Nicholson and Kettelman (1984) argued that distance meter mounted to a theodolite can provide three dimensional survey system.

One of the most important requirements from surveying instruments by the surveyors is reduction of calculation time in order to increase productivity. From time of inventing FACET calculator, the majority of calculation could be done inside the instruments for example resection and triangulation. Since 1960's, program calculator capability has increased 100 times, while considerably their size and price reduced (Hodges et al., 1982). Recently, total station can do the complex calculation on board besides recording information for instance free station calculation. The freestation is a calculation of unknown point position from two or more known points. In addition, data can downloaded from CAD software to the survey instruments for staking out in the field.

2.3 An Overview of Total Station Development

The Total Station was introduced in 1971. TS instruments integrated of an Electronic Distance Measurement EDM which is used to direct distance measurements, and an electronic theodolite which is used to zenith (vertical) and horizontal angles between the target and instrument. The Total Station has the ability to measure distance and angle at once. Its accuracy is very high its in (mm). TS developed and recognized as a single instrument which has the ability to measure and record all field data automatically. Recently, total station can do the complex calculation on board besides recording information for instance freestation calculation. The total station types, surveying procedures and all auxiliary equipment's have a direct effect on the survey recordings and thus the derived mark positions of control survey and uncertainties. There are several different types of total stations available now. They have designed for a variety of different precision requirements and applications. In addition, there are many of different types of auxiliary equipment (levelling and centring devices, tripods, and prisms) they work with survey total stations. All auxiliary equipment and TS instruments are uniquely identified with serial number and they are calibrated on a regular basis (ICSM, 2013). Total stations (TS) are electronic distance and angle measuring devices unremarkably utilized in the geodetic observations. Although, these tools are largely used for outdoor measurements, which has been using sensible optics and precision angle measuring systems motivates scientists to use TS in laboratory observations. Since there are two angle encoders (horizontal and vertical) embedded in TS, it is important to perform the calibration of these instruments so as to see systematic errors (Šiaudinytė, et al., 2015).

2.4 Traverse Adjustment Methods

Traverse adjustment is required to provide a mathematically closed figure by making closure in latitudes as well as closed departures. Methods for adjustment of traverse are classified into two types: approximate methods and rigorous methods.

The approximate methods for traverse adjustment are based on the conditions prevailing in the combinations of linear and angular precision in the observations. On these basis, conditions are divided into three types; precision in angular observation is higher than in

linear measurement, precision in angular as well as in linear measurements are same, and precision in linear observation is more than that in angular measurement.

The least square method provides the most rigorous traverse adjustment method, which allows variation in precision in the observations, decreases random variations to the minimum value in the measurements provides the best position estimations for of all traverse stations, and yields statistics relative to the accuracies of adjusted positions and observations. This method does require more of a computational attempt than the approximate adjustment methods. However, the results are well worth effort. Rest of the traverse adjustment methods are:

2.4.1 Compass Adjustment Method

The Bowditch has illustrated that the correction should be undertaken to the latitude and departure of each course to the total correction in latitude and departure as the course length to the traverse length. This method assumed that the traversing errors are happening by chance and varying with the square root of sides' lengths. Also, he assumed that the effect of distance measuring errors equal to the effect of angular errors (Duggal, 2013). The compass or Bowditch rule which was named after the distinguished American navigator Nathaniel Bowditch (1773-1838), it is a very popular rule for adjusting a closed traverse (Duggal, 2013). The compass method is based on the assumption that all lengths were measured with equal care and all angles taken with approximately the same precision. It is also assumed that the errors in the measurement are accidental and that the total error in any side of the traverse is directly proportional to the total length of the traverse. The compass can work as; the corrections should be applied to the departure (or latitude) of each courses are equal to the total closure in departure (or latitude) multiplied by the ratio of the length of the course to the total length or perimeter of the traverse. These corrections are given by the following equations

$$c_l = C_L (d/D) \tag{2. 1}$$

$$c_d = C_D (d/D) \tag{2. 2}$$

Where:

c_l is the correction should be applied to the latitude of any course

c_d is the correction should be applied to the departure of any course

C_L is the total closure in latitude or the algebraic sum of the north and south latitudes ($\Sigma NL + \Sigma SL$)

C_D = total closure in departure or the algebraic sum of the east and west departures ($\Sigma ED + \Sigma WD$)

d = length of any course

D = total length or perimeter of the traverse

To determine the adjusted latitude of any course the latitude correction is either added to or subtracted from the computed latitude of the course. A simple rule to remember is: If the sums of the northing latitudes exceed the sums of the southing latitudes, latitude corrections are subtracted from the north latitudes and added to the corresponding south latitudes. However, if the sum of the south latitudes exceeds the sum of the north latitudes, the corrections are applied in the opposite manner.

2.4.2 Transit Adjustment Method

The Transit method illustrated that the correction should be applied to the latitude and departure of each courses to the total correction in latitude and departure as the latitude and departure of that courses to the arithmetic sum of the all traverse's latitudes and departures. Also, it assumed that the traversing errors happen by chance or accidental and that the effects of distance measurement errors are greater than the effects of angular measurements errors (Duggal, 2013). The transit rule has no sound theoretical foundation since it is purely empirical. The rule is based on the assumption that the measurements of angles are more precise and accurate than the linear measurements and that the traversing errors are accidental. These corrections are given by the following equations

$$c_l = \text{Lat } (C_L) / (\Sigma N_L - \Sigma S_L) \quad (2.3)$$

$$c_d = \text{Dep } (C_D) / (\Sigma E_D - \Sigma W_D) \quad (2.4)$$

Where:

c_l is the correction should be applied to the latitude of any course

c_d is the correction should be applied to the departure of any course

C_L is the total closure in latitude or the algebraic sum of the north and south latitudes ($\Sigma N_L + \Sigma S_L$)

C_D = total closure in departure or the algebraic sum of the east and west departures ($\Sigma E_D + \Sigma W_D$)

Since the north latitudes are positive quantities and south latitudes are negative quantities, the arithmetical sum of all latitudes is obtained if the summation of south latitudes is subtracted from the summation of north latitudes. Similarly, the arithmetical sum of all departures is obtained if the summation of west departures is subtracted from the summation of east departures since east and west departures are positive and negative quantities, respectively.

2.4.3 Tuttle's Adjustment Method

Sprinsky (1987) has reported the Bowditch's and Crandall's procedure established theoretical formulation based on the minimum sum of the technique of squares which the corrections of departures and latitudes were defined. They tried to simplify the established equation's solution that was ended up with different forms of least square results. The drawback of Crandall's and Bowditch's method was discussed by Tuttle in 1901. The first drawback is distance error changes as the distance square root. The second drawback is error in angle and distance has the same effect.

The Tuttle showed the Crandall's and Compass's method's formulation as follows:

$$X \left[\sum \frac{L_i^2}{d_i} + \rho^2 \sum \frac{D_i^2}{d_i} \right] + \left[(1 - \rho^2) \sum \frac{L_i D_i}{d_i} \right] y + q_1 = 0 \quad (2.5)$$

$$X \left[(1 - \rho^2) \sum \frac{L_i D_i}{d_i} \right] + \left[\rho^2 \sum \frac{L_i^2}{d_i} + \sum \frac{D_i^2}{d_i} \right] y + q_2 = 0 \quad (2.6)$$

$$\rho_i = \frac{\text{azimuth's probable error } i \times \text{distance } i}{\text{distance probable error } i} \quad (2.7)$$

Where, the sum of all observation points q_1 and q_2 are the latitude and departure errors respectively or they are misclosure.

These equations were developed that is different from the Tuttle's original assumption, which the standard errors used in elevation of ρ_i . the distance errors are proportional to the distance themselves, which are in the current DSM instruments changed to:

$$X [\sum Li^2 + \rho^2 \sum Di^2] + [(1 - \rho^2) \sum LiDi] y + q_1 = 0 \quad (2. 8)$$

$$X [\sum(1 - \rho^2) \sum LiDi] + [\rho^2 \sum Li^2 + \sum Di^2] y + q_2 = 0 \quad (2. 9)$$

Tuttle made ρ^2 constant and made the different solution from least square results, but its difference less than the Bowditch's and Crandall's result.

Then the departure and latitude corrected as follows:

$$\nu Li = X [Li^2 + \rho^2 Di^2] + y(1 - \rho^2) LiDi \quad (2. 10)$$

$$\nu Di = X(1 - \rho^2) LiDi + [Li^2 + \rho^2 Di^2] \quad (2. 11)$$

$$\text{Where } y = \frac{-q_2 [\sum Li^2 + \rho^2 \sum Di^2] + q_1 [(1 - \rho^2) \sum LiDi]}{[\sum Li^2 + \rho^2 \sum Di^2] [\rho^2 \sum Li^2 + \sum Di^2] - [(1 - \rho^2)^2 \sum (LiDi)^2]} \quad (2. 12)$$

$$\text{And } X = \frac{-[q_1 + (1 - \rho^2) \sum LiDi]}{[\sum Li^2 + \rho^2 \sum Di^2]} \quad (2. 13)$$

Where the x and y are constant used to minimization, they were used by Crandall.

The result of Bowditch rule with the error of distance vary with distance itself in the case of ρ is unity. But the Crandall method result with the same distance weighting in case of $\rho = 0$, the function of interior angle and azimuth start from the first azimuth A_1 in the traverse surveying. Thus;

$$A_2 = A_1 + 180 - (I_2 + \omega) \quad (2. 14)$$

$$A_3 = A_1 + 360 - (I_2 + I_3 + 2\omega) \quad (2. 15)$$

$$A_i = A_1 + (i - 1) + 180 - \sum (I_i + \omega)$$

Where; the sum is over courses 2 to i , and $\omega = (n - 1) * 180 - \sum I_i / n$;

Where; this sum is over all the n observed angles.

The initial azimuth and interior angles assumed zero which are statistically independent.

$$\sigma_{Ai}^2 = \sigma_{A1}^2 + \sigma_{Ij}^2 + [i - 1/n] 2 \sum \sigma_{Ik}^2 \quad (2. 16)$$

where: $2 \leq j \leq i$ and $1 \leq k \leq n$

For DEM the standard errors are:

$$\sigma_{di} = a + b * di / 1000000 \quad (2. 17)$$

$$\rho^2 = (1/n) \sum (\sigma_{di}^2 + di^2) / \sigma_{di}^2 \quad (2. 18)$$

Where, the sum is applied for the n observed courses.

This procedure is perfect to the closed traverse.

2.4.4 Crandall Adjustment Method

Charles Crandall established the adjustment for traversing errors which is known as his name Crandall's method and published in 1914 (Hazelton, 2008). The method was based on assumption that the angle measurement better than the distance measurement. This meant that all misclosure or errors come from the distance alone. For his solution, Crandall used the least square adjustment by condition equation while he avoided from adjustment angles. This led to reduce the number of adjustments to two, and this made the solution easier.

The traverse angle misclosure adjusted by justifiable or reasonable means. The error can be divided among the traverse angles as Hazelton reported (2008). The bigger amount could be given to the less reliable angles. The angle should adjust to bring misclosure zero. After, adjusting angular misclosure and making it zeros. Now the traverse has only two condition, the solution can be done by 2 X 2 matrix, also the condition least square can be performed. This method of adjustment only for the length of the traverse sides.

If each line length of the traverse is M_i , and θ_i is the traverse azimuth, d_i is the adjusted each line length of the traverse, and v_i is the correction to the measured length of each line to gain the adjusted length:

$$d_i = M_i + v_i \quad (2.19)$$

The conditions to be met can be expressed as:

$$d_1 \cos \theta_1 + d_2 \cos \theta_2 + d_3 \cos \theta_3 + \dots = 0 \text{ (Sum of latitudes equals zero)} \quad (2.20)$$

$$d_1 \sin \theta_1 + d_2 \sin \theta_2 + d_3 \sin \theta_3 + \dots = 0 \text{ (Sum of departures equals zero)} \quad (2.21)$$

Re-arranging and gathering above equations give:

$$(M_1 + v_1) \cos \theta_1 + (M_2 + v_2) \cos \theta_2 + (M_3 + v_3) \cos \theta_3 + \dots = 0$$

$$(M_1 + v_1) \sin \theta_1 + (M_2 + v_2) \sin \theta_2 + (M_3 + v_3) \sin \theta_3 + \dots = 0$$

Re-arranging and gathering terms produces:

$$v_1 \cos \theta_1 + v_2 \cos \theta_2 + v_3 \cos \theta_3 + \dots + q_1 = 0 \quad (2.22)$$

$$v_1 \sin \theta_1 + v_2 \sin \theta_2 + v_3 \sin \theta_3 + \dots + q_2 = 0 \quad (2.23)$$

Where

$$q_1 = M_1 \cos \theta_1 + M_2 \cos \theta_2 + M_3 \cos \theta_3 + \dots = \text{Misclosure in latitude}$$

$$q_2 = M_1 \sin \theta_1 + M_2 \sin \theta_2 + M_3 \sin \theta_3 + \dots = \text{Misclosure in departure}$$

And, q_1 and q_2 are obtained directly from the closure check of the traverse, after adjusting angles the azimuth should be computed. Where D_i is departure and L_i is latitude.

$$v_1 \cos L_1 / d_1 + v_2 \cos L_2 / d_2 + v_3 \cos L_3 / d_3 + \dots + q_1 = 0 \quad (2.24)$$

$$v_1 \sin D_1 / d_1 + v_2 \sin D_2 / d_2 + v_3 \sin D_3 / d_3 + \dots + q_2 = 0 \quad (2.25)$$

Crandall considered two assumptions or cases; the first one is the situation where the errors side length increase in proportion to the square root length of line. That is a reasonable assumption for chain measured distance. The second case is where the

distance errors increase in proportion to the length of line. As a result, the equations become:

$$A \sum Li^2 + B \sum DiLi + q_1 = 0 \quad (2. 26)$$

$$A \sum DiLi + B \sum Di^2 + q_2 = 0 \quad (2. 27)$$

Where the A and B are correctives:

$$A = \frac{[q_2 \sum LiDi - q_1 \sum Di^2]}{[\sum Di^2 \sum Li^2 - (\sum DiLi)^2]}$$

$$B = \frac{[q_1 \sum LiDi - q_2 \sum Li^2]}{[\sum Di^2 \sum Li^2 - (\sum DiLi)^2]}$$

Then the length correction can be calculated as:

$$Vi = Li di A + Di di B \quad (2. 28)$$

2.4.5 Minimum Variance or Least Square Adjustment Method

Sprinsky (1987) and Deakin (1991) have reported that the least square solution has ability to use in all coordinate geometry programs, which is an application of Crandall's method. This method addressed all drawbacks which were done in all other methods. In this method the surveyor can have effect and role in the solutions by using the observations' values and quality (Deakin, 1991). For single closed traverse distances and angles observed, and the initial azimuth addressed as an observation. The Sprinsky reported the single closed traverse has three conditions; which they are the sums of departure and latitude, and the sum of the interior angles equations of the traverse.

For the complete observations in closed traverse the equation of errors is:

$$\sum Li^2 + \text{Start station of northing} - \text{end station of northing} = 0 \quad (2. 29)$$

$$\sum Di^2 + \text{Start station of northing} - \text{end station of northing} = 0 \quad (2. 30)$$

$$\sum Li = (n - 2) * 180 = 0 \quad (2. 31)$$

Where; the summation has done for the n observed courses. This the solution becomes:

$$V = -SB^t (BSB^t)^{-1} W \quad (2. 32)$$

Where: mVi = corrections to observations;

mSm = the observations' dispersion matrix;

$3B_m$ = matrix of partial derivatives of the conditions with respect to the observations in order;

$3Wi$ = the equations of condition, evaluated at the observed values.

Sprinsky reported (1987) that the reason behind choosing this method is the number of correlate equations is not having direct relation to the number of unknown stations should be positioned.

2.5 Resection

Resection has defined in several different ways in the last century. The most significant and relevant definition is; resection is the technique of positioning a new control point by observing three or more control points from that point (Song et al. 2016). Moreover, there

are two types of measurement have been conducting for resection networks; horizontal directions and horizontal distances. The position named freestation.

The resection solutions are varying which they include geometrical, graphical, numerical, and analytical methods. Bock (1959) reported that the numbers of different procedures for calculating resection problems are exceeding 500 procedures. Although, these procedures were designed before inventing computer. Hence, most of the procedures graphical in nature or numerically adjusted which they required to aid of tables.

In the last few decades, several analytical methods have formulated, for instance Collins method, Kaestner-Burkhardt method and Cassini method (Burtch, 2005). In reality, in the procedures of all of these methods the location of resected point (p) is determined in the Cartesian coordinates. This can be done with the different geometrical relations between the position of four points (A, B, C, and P) and the angles.

The different method of resection is the Tienstra method, also known as the barycentric method (Allan et al. 1968). The method provides the position of point (P) in term of barycentric coordinates, which is linear combination of the station's coordinates.

2.5.1 Kaestner-Burkhardt Method

The Kaestner-Burkhardt approach (Blachut et al. 1979; Faig, 1972; Kissam, 1981), also referred to as the Pothot-Snellius method (Allan et al. 1968) is the analytical method. This method depends on the three known coordinate's points A, B, and C and the angles α and β measured at point P as can see in figure 1.

Figure 1, three point resection problem using Kaestner-Burkhardt method

The observed angles are used to calculate ϕ and θ that they contribute to calculate c_1 , c_2 , s , AZ_{AP} and AZ_{BP} .

$$\alpha + \beta + \gamma + \phi + \theta = 360^\circ \quad (2.33)$$

$$c_1 = a \frac{\sin \gamma_1}{\sin \alpha} = a \frac{\sin [180^\circ - (\alpha + \phi)]}{\sin \alpha} = a \frac{\sin(\alpha + \phi)}{\sin \alpha} \quad (2.34)$$

$$c_2 = b \frac{\sin \gamma_2}{\sin \beta} = b \frac{\sin [180^\circ - (\beta + \theta)]}{\sin \beta} = b \frac{\sin(\beta + \theta)}{\sin \beta} \quad (2.35)$$

$$AZ_{AP} = AZ_{AC} + \phi \quad (2.36)$$

$$AZ_{BP} = AZ_{BC} - \theta \quad (2.37)$$

$$X_P = X_A + C_1 \sin AZ_{AP} = X_B + C_2 \sin AZ_{BP} \quad (2.38)$$

$$Y_P = Y_A + C_1 \cos AZ_{AP} = Y_B + C_2 \cos AZ_{BP} \quad (2.39)$$

2.5.2 Collins Point Method

The Collins or Bessel's method (Blachut et al, 1979; Faig, 197; Zeimann, 1974) is an analytical method with the aid of two observed angles α and β . In this method the problem is broken down into two intersections. The two control points and resected point P have to be on a circle circumference (as A, B, and P, in figure 2). The line from P to C is extended until it intersects the circle at a point labelled H. This point is called the Collins' Auxiliary Point. Also, extend of line PC is intersected with circle at point H. This point is Collins auxiliary point.

Figure 2, three point resection problems using the Collins method

$$AZ_{AP} = AZ_{CP} - \alpha \quad (2.40)$$

$$AZ_{BP} = AZ_{CP} + \beta \quad (2.41)$$

$$\Phi = AZ_{AP} - AZ_{AC} \quad (2.42)$$

$$\psi = AZ_{BC} - AZ_{BP} \quad (2.43)$$

$$X_P = X_A + D_{AP} \sin AZ_{AP} = X_B + D_{BP} \sin AZ_{BP} \quad (2.44)$$

$$Y_P = Y_A + D_{AP} \cos AZ_{AP} = Y_B + D_{BP} \cos AZ_{BP} \quad (2.45)$$

2.5.3 Cassini Method

The Cassini approach (Blachut et al. 1979; Faig, 1972; Ziemann, 1974) have illustrated that the Cassini approach of the three-point resection problem is a geometric approach. This method breaks the problem down to an intersection of two circles where one of the intersection points is the unknown point P while the other are; one of the three control points with the aid of two observed angles α and β . This is depicted in figure 3

Figure 3, three point resection problem as proposed by Cassini

$$Y_P = \frac{n Y_{H_1} + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right) Y_C + X_C - X_{H_1}}{N} \quad (2.46)$$

$$X_P = \frac{n X_C + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right) X_{H_1} + Y_C - Y_{H_1}}{N} \quad (2.47)$$

Where: $n = \tan AZ_{H_1P}$
 $N = n + (1/n)$

2.5.4 Tienstra Method

Bannister et al. (1984) have reported that this method refers to as Barycentric. The method has proved mathematically by Porta and Thomas (2009), and Hu and Kuang (1998), and they have illustrated that the method provides the most compact and elegant solution. However, calculations are based on the simple trigonometric formulas with the aid of three observed angles γ , α and β .

(Figure 4, (a) three point resection problem using the Tienstra Method. (b) Basic geometry outlining the principles of the Tienstra Method

$$X_P = \frac{L_1 X_A + L_2 X_B + L_3 X_C}{L_1 + L_2 + L_3} \quad (2.48)$$

$$Y_P = \frac{L_1 Y_A + L_2 Y_B + L_3 Y_C}{L_1 + L_2 + L_3} \quad (2.49)$$

Where:

$$L_1 = \cot 3 + \cot 6$$

$$L_2 = \cot 2 + \cot 5$$

$$L_3 = \cot 4 + \cot 1$$

2.5.5 Method of Direct Distance-Based Positioning Without Redundancy

Easa (2007) has described the direct distance-based method which observes two or more distances from or to the control stations, in order to calculate the position of the resected point P. This method provides two results. The valid solution depends on the geometric properties of position of point.

Figure 5, the direct distance-based positioning method (Easa, 2007)

$$SA^2 = (X_P - X_A)^2 + (Y_P - Y_A)^2 \quad (2.50)$$

$$SB^2 = (X_P - X_B)^2 + (Y_P - Y_B)^2 \quad (2.51)$$

$$SC^2 = (X_P - X_C)^2 + (Y_P - Y_C)^2 \quad (2.52)$$

$$SA^2 - SB^2 = M_1 X_P + M_2 Y_P + M_4 \quad (2.53)$$

Where:

$$M_1 = 2(X_B - X_A)$$

$$M_2 = 2(Y_B - Y_A)$$

$$M_4 = (X_A^2 + Y_A^2) - (X_B^2 + Y_B^2)$$

$$Y_B = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} \quad (2.54)$$

2.5.6 Numerical Method for Solving Horizontal Resection

Numerical method has used the basic mathematical formulas from the geometry of coordinates (Dekov, 2012). This method provides good performance and accuracy. Three known point coordinates and two observed angles APB and BPC are used for resecting point P. as illustrated in figure 6.

Figure 6, three point resection Numerical Method (Dekov, 2012)

The three control points are A (a_1, a_2), B (b_1, b_2) and C (c_1, c_2), and two observed angles are APB and BPC.

$$\cos(\angle APB) * \sqrt{(x_1 - a_1)^2 + (x_2 - a_2)^2} * \sqrt{(x_1 - b_1)^2 + (x_2 - b_2)^2} - [(x_1 - a_1)(x_1 - b_1) + (x_2 - a_2)(x_2 - b_2)] = 0 \quad (2.55)$$

$$\cos(\angle BPC) * \sqrt{(x_1 - b_1)^2 + (x_2 - b_2)^2} * \sqrt{(x_1 - c_1)^2 + (x_2 - c_2)^2} - [(x_1 - b_1)(x_1 - c_1) + (x_2 - b_2)(x_2 - c_2)] = 0 \quad (2.56)$$

3. ASSESSMENT OF THE EXISTING METHODS

3.1 Overview

In the previous chapter, all the proposed methods in the literature that account misclosure from both latitude and departure in traverse adjustment were discussed. Furthermore, a brief introduction to the types of the adjustment methods, namely, and design-oriented methods are presented. The most of the adjustment methods are simple and engineers can simply implement them. Therefore, this research is more concentrated on the adjustment methods. Furthermore, some of these methods were also investigated by other reliable authors. Therefore, in this piece of work they are not evaluated again.

On the other hand, the new proposed adjustment method includes resection, there are several reliable resection methods were discussed in the literature. They were briefly introduced and the way how they designed were illustrated. This chapter will discuss a critical review of traverse adjustment methods and assess the resection methods.

3.2 Critical Review of Traverse Adjustment Methods

Traverse is calculated in planes. The most popular horizontal positioning technique is the system of orthogonal coordinate which has dominated in construction and land survey (Sprinsky, 1987). There are many methods widely used to traverse adjustment such as, Crandall's method, transit rule, and minimum variance application or least square method. In transit rule the result of station coordinates determined by the system of coordinate which was chosen for survey. In contrast, there is no doubt with the reality of compass rule which can provide regular coordinate from irregular data (Sprinsky, 1987). The method of adjusting a traverse by the transit is similar to the method using the compass rule (Duggal, 2013). The main difference is that in the transit rule the latitude and departure corrections depend on the length of the latitude and departure of the course respectively instead of both depending on the length of the course. This method proposed by Bowditch to solve that problem constituted for Robert Patterson in 1808 in *The Analyst*; for adjusting observations were required to statistical consideration, for example adjusting distances and azimuths in traverse (Stoughton, 1974; Sprinsky, 1987). The transit rule can work as; the correction should be applied to the departure (or latitude) of each course is equal to the departure (or latitude) of the course multiplied by the ratio of the total closure in departure (or latitude) to the arithmetic sum of all the latitudes (or departures) of the traverse. The Bowditch's method was the graphical solution. In 1808 Adrian formulated Bowditch's solution as an application of least square principles (Tuttle, 1901; Sprinsky, 1987). Crandall (1901) tried to update Bowditch's and Aderina's solution depends on the instrumentation of his era. Also, Crandall selected some problems which Compass rule was based on, in the statistical assumptions for example the observed distances' probable errors are proportional to the distances' square root of themselves, and assumes of compass method that is the distance measurement's probable error is equal to the bearing probable error multiplied to the distance (Crandall, 1901). However, Crandall considered that the azimuths are more accurate than distances, and also established the calculation of misclosure on the same assumption. This assumption is unrealistic for the recent engineering surveying instruments especially for electronic instruments, unlike to the compass rule.

The correction should be done against statistical methods that show the most anticipated solution. The least square is the best solutions (Sprinsky, 1987) which can minimize the

sum have weighted of squares of the observation coordinates. The adjustment must be from the rest of standard errors of distance, direction, azimuth, and angle. Also, the correction of observations must be consisting on the quality of observations. The surveyors could say this method is choice for solution and the other methods are unnecessary. One of the most effective advantage of this method is can be written as a program for every microcomputer, and the user does not need to have the very high mathematical background to know how the program does work. In addition, this method makes systematic errors in the field. This helps surveyors to do not require to calculator or computer in the field to deal with adjustment and the adjusted observations (Sprinsky, 1987). "*As an office procedure the least square algorithm is the method of choice*" (Sprinsky, 1987). This method does not use the error propagation to find azimuth's variances. In this method of solution, if the initial azimuth is fixed by assuming or defining it, the small variances can acquire from observation.

This method has much more advantages than as mentions above. One of the other advantages is; it has ability to extend to create additional correlate equation, to adjust more closed traverse, in other word to adjust more than one closed traverse. Also, it can be provided a high quality azimuth with the initial azimuth, unlike to the other methods for instance Compass, Crandall, and Tuttle's method.

From the condition or correlates method the matrix can be used to prevent the possible size of least square solution to the micro computer applications. Most of survey data can be adjusted by compass Bowditch's rule which is the widest spread technique, While, the compass rule does not provide effective adjustment. For the distance measurement either by chains or electronically the compass rule applies the same correction for both of them. In addition, it provides similar correction for azimuths, angles, and directions. Nevertheless, the least square solution and Tuttle's method have no this drawback. On the other hand, the resection methods will be assessed in this chapter.

3.3 Assessments of Resection Methods

The resection solutions are varying which they include geometrical, graphical, numerical, and analytical methods. Bock in (1959) reported that the numbers of different procedures for calculating resection problems are exceeding 500 procedures; most of them are graphical methods. All the analytical solutions provide accurate and fast solutions. Moreover, they are suitable for computer implementations. However, long descriptions and relative complication are in their drawbacks. The numerical solutions are easy in calculation, and they use very basic mathematical formulas, also they are suitable for computer implementations. In addition, the analytical methods are faster than the numerical methods. The graphical methods are difficult in calculation they appear before inventing computers. They cannot be easy to use them in computer programs but they can provide solution in the field.

3.3.1 Kaestner-Burkhardt Method

Kaestner-Burkhardt method is an analytical method (Burtch, 2005), also referred to as the Pothonot-Snellius method. This analytic solution is suitable for computer implementation and it gives fast and precise solutions. However, this method is relatively complicated, and the description of the method is relatively long. Some modifications were made for this method by the United States Coast and Geodetic Survey (USC and GS, the National Geodetic Survey, NGS). All the modifications of the USC&GS method presented

in Kissam (1981) and with a slight modification in Anderson and Mikhail (1998). By the modifications all of the angles can be calculated, the sine law can be used to found the lengths of the different legs of the triangles.

3.3.2 Collins Method

Basically it is an analytical method. It provides accurate and fast solution. Also, the method is easy to computer programming, suitable for computer implementation, and easy to calculation. Its solution based on the observed angles and three known control points this helps solution to be simple and easy. In addition, the method uses the geometrical, triangulations, and coordinates formulas, but uses an auxiliary point to help solution.

3.3.3 Cassini Method

Basically it is an analytical and graphical method. It provides accurate and fast solution, and easy to computer programming, and suitable for computer implementation. However, its description is quite long and relatively complicated (Dekov, 2012). Moreover, the method needs to auxiliary point for calculation. In addition, it uses only the observed angles and known points in its calculations

3.3.4 Tienstra Method

This method is an analytic method is suitable for computer implementation and it give precise and fast solution but it is relatively complicated, and its description is relatively long. Moreover, it uses only the observed angles and known points in its calculations. This method is a different approach to solve the three-point resection problem, also known as the barycentric method, has singularities Allan et al. (1968); Greulich (1999). If aligning is happened for the stations, that is, if the three known control points are lied on the same line, in this case the method cannot be used, due to degeneration the reference triangle and the coordinates of barycentric are not applicable.

3.3.5 Method of Direct Distance-Based Positioning Without Redundancy

The main difference of the method can be seen from the name; the method uses observed distanced for solutions. This method is very simple in calculation and easy for computer implementation, even can be solved in excel sheet (Easa, 2007). The main advantage of the method can be used for calculating two and three dimensional coordinate. Moreover, the method uses very simple mathematical formulas. The most popular drawback of the method has reported by Easa (2007) "*the method provides two solutions directly. The valid solution can be determined by inspection based on the geometric characteristics of the positioning in the field*"

3.3.6 Numerical Method

The numerical method uses only basic formulae from coordinate geometry. In addition, the numerical method has presented is easy for computer programming and fast enough for computer implementation. Also, the presented numerical method is not fast as the analytical methods (Dekov, 2012). On the other hand, the numerical method has intrinsic singularities. These problem causes to the method provide infinite solutions. Intrinsic singularities are happened if the unknown point and the three known points lie on the same line or on the same circle. Any computer program must detect this problem and send a suitable message about it to inform the user.

4. NEW PROPOSED METHOD

4.1 Overview

Reviewing the literature and evaluating the existing models in preceding chapters have indicated that all of the available methods in the literature can accurately adjust the traverse, and control network survey where the control points visible to each other, where there is no enough space to set up instruments (Total Station), and where using GPS is restricted or limited. Therefore, the need for a new traversing method that considering none visibility of control points, limited space to set up instruments, and restriction or limiting of using GPS.

In this chapter, to the best of author's knowledge, a new traversing method is developed by statistically analysing relevant parameters. The main effective parameters that influence the reliability of proposed method are precision and accuracy. They were considered during observations.

The new method is introduced as Traversing by Resection. Output of the literature and investigations in this thesis have done. This study will be the first research examines traversing by resection.

The important point has to be mentioned is all data were assembled in the field were arranged in a proper format and tables in the Microsoft Excel sheets. Moreover, all gathered data were calculated in the Microsoft Excel sheets. In addition, the AutoCAD software was used as a double check for calculated data.

4.2 The Proposed Method

Outcome of the literature and assessment methods the Collins method going to be used for resecting traverse control points for example, points A, B, C, D, and E as illustrated in the figure 7, as an approximated coordinate. Then, the least square method for the best approach coordinates. The other control points for instance, 1, 2, 3, and 4 as shown in the figure 7, going to be established by measuring azimuths and distances from the point where instrument has set up. For clarifying how the analysis going to be undertaken, point A to point B will be taken as an example from howl, all other parts are repeated of taken example.

Figure 7, a simple sketch of data measurements and calculation steps

4.2.1 Establishing Horizontal Coordinates from Observed Azimuths and Distances

This process can be employed by two mathematical steps; firstly, establishing horizontal control points, and secondly error propagation calculation.

4.2.1.1 Establishing Horizontal Control Points

If point A and points 1, 2, 3, and 4 are taken as an example as shown in figure 8.a. For establishing coordinates of points 1, 2, 3, and 4, Point A is a start point and a known coordinate point. Let's denote points 1, 2, 3, and 4 as i , see figure 8.b.

$$E_i = E_A + \Delta E = E_A + L_{Ai} \sin Az_{Ai} \quad (4.1)$$

$$N_i = N_A + \Delta N = N_A + L_{Ai} \cos Az_{Ai} \quad (4.2)$$

Where:

E_A, N_A are easting and northing of initial control point,

E_i, N_i are easting and northing of established control points,

L_{Ai} is length of the courses, and

Az_{Ai} is azimuth of the of courses from initial control point to established control points

Figure 8, 8.a established horizontal coordinates, 8.b Polar coordinate analysis

4.2.1.2 Error Propagation Calculation

Based on the variance-covariance matrix the uncertainty-error has to be calculated of the position of a point. At the beginning standard errors will be calculated for the azimuths and distances.

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\bar{x} - xi)^2}{n-1}} \quad (4. 3)$$

Where:

σ = standard error or precision of measured distances and azimuths,

xi = individual measurement,

\bar{x} = the arithmetic mean (most probable value), and

n = the number of samples in the data set

The standard errors of azimuths and distance will form a matrix of errors for both measurements, which is uncorrelated.

$$\Sigma_{Az L} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{Az}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_L^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4. 4)$$

Jacobian matrix helps to find Var-Cov matrix

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial E}{\partial Az} & \frac{\partial E}{\partial L} \\ \frac{\partial N}{\partial Az} & \frac{\partial N}{\partial L} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} L \cos Az & \sin Az \\ -L \sin Az & \cos Az \end{bmatrix} \quad (4. 5)$$

Then the Var-Cov matrix of Easting and northing (E, N) is

$$\Sigma_{EN} = J_{EN,LAz} \Sigma_{LAz} J_{EN,LAz}^T = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_E^2 & \sigma_{EN} \\ \sigma_{EN} & \sigma_N^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4. 6)$$

Then, the parameters of error ellipse have to be determined

$$W = \sqrt{(\sigma_E^2 - \sigma_N^2)^2 + 4(\sigma_{EN})^2} \quad (4. 7)$$

$$a = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_E^2 + \sigma_N^2 + W)} \quad (4. 8)$$

$$b = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_E^2 + \sigma_N^2 - W)} \quad (4. 9)$$

$$\tan 2\theta = \frac{2\sigma_{EN}}{\sigma_E^2 - \sigma_N^2} \quad (4. 10)$$

Where:

a = major axis of error ellipse,

b = minor axis of error ellipse, and

θ = anti-clockwise angle starting from axis x to the minor axis.

4.2.2 Establishing Traverse Control Points by Resection

At this phase, the howl process can be done in three main steps; resection using Collins point method as an approximated coordinate, least square method for the best approach coordinate, and error propagation calculations.

4.2.2.1 Resection Using Collins Method

As illustrated in the chapter three this method is an analytical method. It provides accurate and fast solution. Also, the method is easy to computer programming, and suitable for computer implementation, and easy to calculation. Its solution based on the observed angles and three known control points. This helps solution to be simple and easy.

Resection will be applied for the second part of taken example as can be seen in figure 9.a. The point B is traverse control point which it has to be respected. The points 1, 2, 3, and 4 are known control points which they calculated from the section 4.2.1 establishing horizontal coordinates from observed azimuths and distances. All the calculation going to be undertaken based on the sketch that illustrated in figure 9.b.

Figure 9, 9.a Establishing Traverse Control Points by Resection, 9.b Collins Method

The solution involves five distinct steps:

1. The Collins' Auxiliary Point coordinate, H has to be computed, by intersection from both control points 1 and 3.
2. The azimuth Az_{H2} is computed which will also yield the azimuth between 2 and B since $Az_{H2} = Az_{2B}$.
3. The azimuth of the lines 1B and 3B should be computed

$$Az_{1B} = Az_{2B} - \alpha \quad (4.11)$$

$$Az_{3B} = Az_{2B} + \beta \quad (4.12)$$

4. The coordinates of Auxiliary Point can be computed by intersection from 1 and 2 and also from 3 and 2.
5. If required, by using the auxiliary angles φ and ψ the solution can be performed.

$$\varphi = Az_{1B} - Az_{12} \quad (4.13)$$

$$\psi = Az_{32} - Az_{2B} \quad (4.14)$$

Then, using the sine law,

$$D_{1B} = \frac{D_{12} \sin(\alpha + \varphi)}{\sin \alpha} \quad (4. 15)$$

$$D_{3B} = \frac{D_{32} \sin(\beta + \psi)}{\sin \beta} \quad (4. 16)$$

This gives the coordinate of resected point as

$$E_B = E_1 + D_{1B} \sin Az_{1B} = E_3 + D_{3B} \cos Az_{3B} \quad (4. 17)$$

$$N_B = N_1 + D_{1B} \sin Az_{1B} = N_3 + D_{3B} \cos Az_{3B} \quad (4. 18)$$

4.2.2.2 Applied Least Square Method for the Resected Traverse Control Points

The Least Square or Variation of Coordinates should be employed when four or more directions are observed to known control points. The least squares method might be applied to achieve the best estimated coordinates of the resected control point. The least square method needs to the formation of a set of equation of observations that they are required for the best estimates of the resected point coordinates. Owing to the nature of the least square, the equation observations have to be approximately linearized, and the process of their solutions should be iterative. As a first step, the initial values are assumed, corrections are calculated and assumed values are updated. The process is iterated until approximated values become the best approximate, and the corrections become negligible.

This can be employed in four steps:

First step: Observation Equations of the Resection

The resected point is obtained by applying least square method is the best estimated coordinates, in the state of having four or more observed directions to known control points. The set of observation equations require to be formed in the least square method, all the observed equations require for linearization the equation 4.19 whose components are presented in Figure 10 which is taken from the Taylor theorem linearization process.

$$\alpha_k + V_k + Z = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{E_k - E_p}{N_k - N_p} \right] \quad (4. 19)$$

Where:

α_k = the observed directions from resected point P_i to known coordinate points P_k

V_k = the vector of residuals

Z = the reference azimuth of reference control point

E_k, N_k = the coordinates of the control stations

E_p, N_p = the coordinates of the resected point

Figure 10, the observed directions and distances from resected point (RMIT University, 2005).

None linear equation 4.19 is linearized approximately as following equation

$$\alpha_k + V_k + Z^\circ + \Delta Z = \alpha_k \Delta N_P - b_k \Delta E_P + \phi_k^\circ \quad (4.20)$$

Where:

α_k, b_k are representing the coefficient of directions.

$$\alpha_k = \frac{-(E_k - E_P)}{(S_k^\circ)^2} = \frac{-\sin \phi_k^\circ}{S_k} \quad (4.21)$$

$$b_k = \frac{(N_k - N_P)}{(S_k^\circ)^2} = \frac{\cos \phi_k^\circ}{S_k} \quad (4.22)$$

$\Delta E, \Delta N,$ and ΔZ are the achieved corrections to the approximate calculated resected point coordinates E_P°, N_P° and the constant of approximate direction as presented that

$$E_P = E_P^\circ + \Delta E \quad (4.23)$$

$$N_P = N_P^\circ + \Delta N \quad (4.24)$$

$$Z = Z^\circ + \Delta Z \quad (4.25)$$

From the approximate coordinates E_P°, N_P° the distances and azimuths are achieved S_k°, ϕ_k°

$$S_k^\circ = \sqrt{(E_k - E_P^\circ)^2 + (N_k - N_P^\circ)^2} \quad (4.26)$$

$$\phi_k^\circ = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{E_k - E_P^\circ}{N_k - N_P^\circ} \right] \quad (4.27)$$

Second Step: Standard Matrix is formed from the Observation Equations

The equation (4.20) can be written in to standard form

$$V_k + \Delta Z + a_k \Delta N_P + b_k \Delta E_P = \phi_k^\circ - (\alpha_k + Z^\circ) \quad (4. 28)$$

All the observation equations n equations can be re-arranged in the form of matrix as

$$\begin{bmatrix} V1 \\ V2 \\ \vdots \\ Vn \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} a1 & b1 & 1 \\ a2 & b2 & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ an & bn & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta E \\ \Delta N \\ \Delta Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1^\circ - (\alpha_1 + Z^\circ) \\ \phi_2^\circ - (\alpha_2 + Z^\circ) \\ \vdots \\ \phi_n^\circ - (\alpha_n + Z^\circ) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$V + BX = f \quad (4. 29)$$

Where:

n is the number of equations are linearized

u is the unknown's numbers (in the case of a resection u = 3)

B is the matrix coefficients (n, u)

x is a (u, 1) unknown's vectors

f is a computed – observed bearing which is a vector of numeric terms

Third Step: Solution of the Unknown Parameters and Normal Equations Formation

One of the characteristics of the least square adjustment; the precision (variance) of any measurement is related to the other measurements (observations), it is covariance. These computations are included covariance matrix Σ . Practically, the covariance matrix is evaluated by cofactor matrix Q. Where $\Sigma = \sigma_o^2 Q$ is the relation between covariance matrix and cofactor matrix, while σ_o^2 represents variance factor. One of the other characteristic of the least square is expressing relative precision in terms of weight which is inverse propositional to a variance $W = Q^{-1}$. All the three least square parameters covariance matrices, cofactor matrices and weight matrices are symmetric and square.

The least squares principles are applied to equation (4.29) with the observation's precisions were estimated by a weighted matrix will form normal equations as

$$(B^T W B)X = B^T W f$$

$$\text{Or } NX = t \quad (4. 30)$$

Where:

B^T = Weighted matrix

$N = B^T W B$ = Matrix coefficient of normal equations

$t = B^T W f$ = Vector of numeric terms

In this case the number of unknowns are three n = 3

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta N \\ \Delta E \\ \Delta Z \end{bmatrix} = N^{-1} t \quad (4. 31)$$

Fourth Step: Formation of the parameters; Coefficient Matrix N and Vector of Numeric Terms t

The both vector of numeric terms and coefficient matrix (f, B) for the number of (n) observations have these forms

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & 1 \\ a_2 & b_2 & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_n & b_n & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{f} = \begin{bmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \\ \vdots \\ f_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1^\circ - (\alpha_1 + Z^\circ) \\ \phi_2^\circ - (\alpha_2 + Z^\circ) \\ \vdots \\ \phi_n^\circ - (\alpha_n + Z^\circ) \end{bmatrix}$$

The associated variance σ^2 indicates the precision of observed directions which estimated by S^2 where σ is the standard deviation and S is its estimate. The covariances between measurements are zero and the cofactor matrix, weight matrix, and covariance matrix are all diagonal matrices. The weight matrix W and the cofactor matrix Q have new form

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} s_1^2 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & s_2^2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & s_3^2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & s_n^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{Q}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/s_1^2 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1/s_2^2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/s_3^2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1/s_n^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} w_1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & w_2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & w_3 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & w_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.32)$$

The vector of numeric terms t and coefficient matrix N of normal equation have the new form

$$\mathbf{N} = \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{k=1}^n w_k a_k^2 & \sum_{k=1}^n w_k a_k b_k & \sum_{k=1}^n w_k a_k \\ \sum_{k=1}^n w_k a_k b_k & \sum_{k=1}^n w_k b_k^2 & \sum_{k=1}^n w_k b_k \\ \sum_{k=1}^n w_k a_k & \sum_{k=1}^n w_k b_k & \sum_{k=1}^n w_k \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{f} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{k=1}^n w_k a_k f_k \\ \sum_{k=1}^n w_k b_k f_k \\ \sum_{k=1}^n w_k f_k \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.33)$$

The coefficient matrix B and vector of numeric terms f are divided by the suitable estimate of the standard deviation which they form augmented matrices $\bar{\mathbf{B}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{f}}$ as

$$\bar{\mathbf{B}} = \begin{bmatrix} a_1/s_1 & b_1/s_1 & 1/s_1 \\ a_2/s_2 & b_2/s_2 & 1/s_2 \\ a_3/s_3 & b_3/s_3 & 1/s_3 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_n/s_n & b_n/s_n & 1/s_n \end{bmatrix}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{f}} = \begin{bmatrix} f_1/s_1 \\ f_2/s_2 \\ f_3/s_3 \\ \vdots \\ f_n/s_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (\phi_1^0 - \alpha_1 + z^0)/s_1 \\ (\phi_2^0 - \alpha_2 + z^0)/s_2 \\ (\phi_3^0 - \alpha_3 + z^0)/s_3 \\ \vdots \\ (\phi_n^0 - \alpha_n + z^0)/s_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.34)$$

Hence, the normal equation coefficient matrix \mathbf{N} and vector of numeric terms \mathbf{t} can be representing as

$$\mathbf{N} = \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{B} = \bar{\mathbf{B}}^T \bar{\mathbf{B}} \quad (4.35)$$

$$\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{f} = \bar{\mathbf{B}}^T \bar{\mathbf{f}} \quad (4.36)$$

4.2.2.3 The Iterative Solution and Error Propagation (Assessment of Precision)

The approximated of easting and northing coordinates E_p^0, N_p^0 and the approximated orientation constant Z^0 are corrected by the elements of the solution vector $\mathbf{X} = [\Delta X \ \Delta N \ \Delta Z]^T$. The approximate values will be added by the corrections to achieve updated values of the approximations and perform a new iteration.

The iteration solution is employed till the corrections provide the desired solution for example less than 0.5 mm. At this stage the approximate values may be regarded as true or exact values and the solutions are stopped. When the iterative process is finished, the residuals \mathbf{v} is will be computed from equation (4.29). The residuals indicate or assess the quality of measurements which the large residuals indicate poor observations. The residuals can provide estimated variance factor by this equation:

$$\hat{\sigma}_0^2 = \frac{\mathbf{v}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{v}}{n - u} = \frac{\mathbf{f}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{f} - \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{t}}{n - u} \quad (4.37)$$

As mentioned in this chapter, one of the least square adjustment's characteristics is precision computation of the computed quantities which is given by

$$\Sigma_{xx} = \sigma_0^2 \mathbf{Q}_{xx} = \sigma_0^2 \mathbf{N}^{-1} \quad (4.38)$$

From the variance matrix Σ_{xx} , the parameters of standard error ellipse can be calculated which they are the major and minor axes of the error ellipse, and the angle between the E-axis and the major axis (positive anti-clockwise) of the error ellipse, they are

$$W = \sqrt{(\sigma_E^2 - \sigma_N^2)^2 + 4(\sigma_{EN})^2} \quad (4.39)$$

$$a = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_E^2 + \sigma_N^2 + W)} \quad (4.40)$$

$$b = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(s_E^2 + s_N^2 - W)} \quad (4.41)$$

$$\tan 2\theta = \frac{2\sigma_{EN}}{\sigma_E^2 - \sigma_N^2} \quad (4.42)$$

Where:

a = major axis

b = minor axis

θ = the angle between the E-axis and the major axis (positive anti-clockwise)

4.3 The Project Flow Diagram

CHAPTER 5: DATA MEASUREMENT AND ANALYSIS, AND ASSESSMENT OF THE NEW METHOD

5.1 Overview

In this chapter, the assembled data in the field will be presented in the proper formats and tables. Moreover, the equipment's were used for assembling data will be introduced. In addition, based on the calculation of the gathered data the proposed method will be assessed.

5.2 The Field Description and the Used Instruments

The data gathered in the University of Nottingham, Jubilee campus, which is located in the United Kingdom, Nottingham City, on the coordinate 52.9359°N 1.2077°W. Three minor points at Jubilee main campus in the figure 12.

Figure 12, Main entrance of Jubilee campus and three observed control points

On the other hand, the data gathered by Robotic Total Station TS60. The Nova TS60 is the revolutionary generation of Leica Captivate software which it has ability to turn very complex data into the workable 3D models and the most realistic. TS60 applications are simple and easy to use and touch screen technology. It has ability to view all forms of design and measured data in all dimensions. This TS generation can easy work with GNSS, total stations alone and/or both. This total station offers satisfactory precision in the harshest conditions, which is designed for the highest accuracy down to the sub-second and sub-millimetre. The instrument can be seen the figure 13.

Figure 13, Robotic Total Station TS60

5.3 Data Measurements

Ten trials of raw data were gathered by TS60 with face left and face right readings. They are consisting of four trials with four observations two of them with small angle measurement and the other two with open angle measurement. Three of them with five observations are different angular measurements. The last three measurements with six observations are different angular observation. The reasons behind these differences are to compare the different number of observation. In addition, examine the different angular measurements, and how repeating measurements affects the quality of the results. All observations are with five main control stations. All data were modified into azimuths and distances from the main control points to establish the minor control points, and directions from minor control points to resect main control points. A sample of measured data is presented in the following tables and the others are putted in appendix.

Readings from point A				
	Azimuths			Distances
units	d	m	s	m
p1	102	49	12	53.175
p2	117	7	18	46.166
p3	133	46	45	42.701
p4	144	1	54	26.931
p5	159	37	44	31.782
p6	172	11	22	35.259
Readings from point B				
p7	85	24	39	37.74
p8	101	58	48	42.154
p9	110	32	59	42.58
p10	125	21	6	47.657
p11	135	13	50	31.623
p12	164	28	21	24.621
Readings from point C				

p13	232	47	9	38.504
p14	243	59	50	45.135
p15	264	7	47	32.501
p16	280	12	40	33.591
p17	300	47	58	30.622
p18	321	34	17	32.973
Readings from point D				
p19	13	15	2	20.576
p20	253	0	16	40.072
p21	268	45	37	32.41
p22	299	30	0	21.893
p23	321	17	3	20.864
p24	344	16	57	17.69
Readings from point E				
p25	6	18	10	27.852
p26	32	6	59	18.93
p27	64	2	54	35.497
p28	83	57	58	44.088
p29	329	5	15	47.123
p30	349	2	3	36.543

Table 1, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 3 with six observations

From point B						
	Orientations			Directions		
units	d	m	s	d	m	s
p1	120	46	39	43	6	52
p2	116	33	0	38	53	13
p3	110	17	18	32	37	31
p4	92	12	48	14	33	1
p5	86	40	56	9	1	9
p6	77	39	47	0	0	0
From point C						
p7	39	43	18	9	56	23
p8	47	49	50	18	2	55
p9	50	55	49	21	8	54
p10	59	43	57	29	57	2
p11	44	52	4	15	5	9
p12	29	46	55	0	0	0
From point D						
p13	65	27	0	52	7	13
p14	73	6	4	59	46	17
p15	56	49	23	43	29	44
p16	49	56	26	36	36	39
p17	31	27	28	18	7	41
p18	13	19	47	0	0	0
From point E						
p19	51	8	53	0	0	0
p20	104	32	30	53	23	37
p21	101	25	22	50	16	29
p22	86	30	44	35	21	51
p23	76	46	35	25	37	42
p24	64	45	50	13	36	57
From point A						
p25	75	57	34	36	48	13
p26	65	52	33	26	43	12

p27	56	6	25	16	57	4
p28	39	9	21	0	0	0
p29	86	39	34	47	30	13
p30	82	56	4	43	46	43

Table 2, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 3 with six observations

5.4 Data Analysis and Discussion

All data were collected in the field were arranged in a proper format and tables in the Microsoft Excel sheets. Moreover, all gathered data were calculated in the Microsoft Excel sheets. In addition, the AutoCAD software was used as a double check for calculated data.

After arrangement of observed data, data were calculated. The results have presented for four, five, and six observations trials with easting and northing misclosures respectively in the tables 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8.

No. Of Trials	Benchmark Coord.	Calculated Easting Coord. Least square	Calculated Easting Coord. Collins method	Collins. Method Misclosure	Least square misclosure	Variance matrix of errors σ_E
Trial 1	1000	1000.012	1000.014	0.014	0.012	0.036
Trial 2	1000	1000.006	1000.006	0.006	0.006	0.036
Trial 3	1000	1000.007	1000.007	0.007	0.007	0.036
Trial 4	1000	999.963	999.937	-0.063	-0.037	0.036

Table 3, results of four observation measurements of easting coordinates

No. Of Trials	Benchmark Coord.	Calculated Northing Coord. Least square	Calculated Northing Coord. Collins method	Collins. Method Misclosure	Least square misclosure	Variance matrix of errors σ_N
Trial 1	1000	1000.009	1000.021	0.021	0.009	0.050
Trial 2	1000	999.996	999.996	-0.004	-0.004	0.050
Trial 3	1000	1000.002	1000.002	0.002	0.002	0.050
Trial 4	1000	1000.032	999.994	-0.006	0.032	0.050

Table 4, results of four observation measurements of northing coordinates

No. Of Trials	Benchmark Coord.	Calculated Easting Coord. Least square	Calculated Easting Coord. Collins method	Collins. Method Misclosure	Least square misclosure	Variance matrix of errors σ_E
Trial 1	1000	1000.007	1000.007	0.007	0.007	0.036
Trial 2	1000	1000.003	1000.003	0.003	0.003	0.036
Trial 3	1000	1000.012	1000.005	0.005	0.012	0.036

Table 5, results of five observation measurements of easting coordinates

No. Of Trials	Benchmark Coord.	Calculated Northing Coord. Least square	Calculated Northing Coord. Collins method	Collins. Method Misclosure	Least square misclosure	Variance matrix of errors σ_N
---------------	------------------	---	---	----------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------------------

Trial 1	1000	999.995	999.995	-0.005	-0.005	0.065
Trial 2	1000	1000.002	1000.004	0.004	0.002	0.065
Trial 3	1000	1000.005	999.979	-0.021	0.005	0.065

Table 6, results of five observation measurements of northing coordinates

No. Of Trials	Benchmark Coord.	Calculated Easting Coord. Least square	Calculated Easting Coord. Collins method	Collins. Method Misclosure	Least square misclosure	Variance matrix of errors σE
Trial 1	1000	1000.007	1000.006	0.006	0.007	0.035
Trial 2	1000	1000.002	1000.002	0.002	0.002	0.035
Trial 3	1000	1000.012	1000.004	0.004	0.012	0.035

Table 7, results of six observation measurements of easting coordinates

No. Of Trials	Benchmark Coord.	Calculated Northing Coord. Least square	Calculated Northing Coord. Collins method	Collins. Method Misclosure	Least square misclosure	Variance matrix of errors σN
Trial 1	1000	999.997	999.996	-0.004	-0.003	0.072
Trial 2	1000	1000.002	1000.002	0.002	0.002	0.072
Trial 3	1000	1000.005	999.980	-0.020	0.005	0.072

Table 8, results of six observation measurements of northing coordinates

The above results are generally indicating the quality of measurements. Misclosures for both methods; Collins point method and least square method are quite accurate and precise because most of the results are occurring in the range of $\pm\sigma$ standard errors which is normally in any engineering surveying measurements %68 of sample occurring in this range based on figure 14 standard graph for accuracy and precision (confident level graph).

Figure 14, standard graph for accuracy and precision (confident level graph)

There are 20 misclosures for both easting and northing coordinates from least square calculation. As a result, 19 out of 20 misclosures are in range $\pm\sigma$ it represents %95 of samples. Furthermore, 1 out of 20 misclosures in range $\pm 2\sigma$ which is equivalent to %5 of samples, the accuracy and precision of trials presented in the following graphs. These results are might be reasonable start to thinking about depending on the resection points as a control point. The Collins method results are the same as least square results.

Figure 15, Confident level for easting misclosure of four observations measurements

Figure 16, Confident level for northing misclosure of four observations measurements

Regarding to the tables 3 and 4, these two graphs in figure 15 and 16 are four observation measurements. They present that from four eastings and four northings only one misclosure is in the range $\pm 2\sigma$ which is the easting of trial 4, and others are in the range $\pm\sigma$. They are precise and reliable data.

Figure 17, Confident level for easting misclosure of five observations measurements

Figure 18, Confident level for northing misclosure of five observations measurements

Regarding to the tables 5 and 6, these two graphs 17 and 18 they are five observation measurements. All trials are in the high quality of measurements which all the trials either for easting or northing are occurred in the limit $\pm\sigma$.

Figure 19, Confident level for easting misclosure of six observations measurements

Figure 20, Confident level for northing misclosure of six observations measurements

Referring to the tables 7 and 8, these two graphs 19 and 20 they are six observation measurements. Such as, the previous one the rest of misclosures are the confident level which is $\pm\sigma$.

Overall, the bell shape graphs of level of confident are illustrated that the measured data is relatively sufficient quality in term of accuracy and precision. In addition, they have indicated that the method of measurement and the geometry of measurements is might be reliable.

The geometry of measurements especially angular measurement has substantial effect on the quality of results. Consider table 3 and 4 the misclosures of trials 1 and 4 about three times bigger than in trials 2 and 3 for example, 0.012 and -0.036 are about three time of 0.004 and 0.002. This difference is coming from the difference of directions which the

directions of trials 1 and 4 $> 30^\circ$ that is a good angular geometry, while the directions of trials 2 and 3 $< 30^\circ$ that is not satisfactory angular geometry.

On the other hand, the methods of calculations affect the quality of results due to considering different parameters and their natures. For instance, Collins point method requires 3 observations while least square method requires four or more than observations. With having the fact that the least square method is the method of best estimation but it gets more errors from measurements due to demand of high number of observations. The following charts are illustrated this situation.

Figure 21, different between Collin and least square method for easting misclosure of four observations measurements

Figure 22, different between Collin and least square method for northing misclosure of four observations measurements

The charts in figures 21 and 22 are showed that in the trials 2 and 3 both methods misclosure are equal. Moreover, in the trials 1 and 4 misclosure of least square is smaller than Collins method. In the trial 4 of northing, the Collins method misclosure smaller than the least square misclosure. Generally, both methods affected the results where they affected by geometry of angular measurements.

Figure 23, different between Collin and least square method for easting misclosure of five observations measurements

Figure 24, different between Collin and least square method for northing misclosure of five observations measurements

From the charts 23 and 24 there are different results between easting and northing. Easting of Collins method result is more accurate than least square results but in northing the least square results are more accurate in general. This happened due increase the number of observations which lead to increase the amount of propagated errors.

Figure 25, different between Collin and least square method for easting misclosure of six observations measurements

Figure 26, different between Collin and least square method for northing misclosure of six observations measurements

Return to the charts 25 and 26 there are different results between easting and northing, such as the five observation measurements' charts. Easting of Collins method result is more accurate than least square results but in northing the least square results are more accurate in general. This happened due increase the number of observations which lead to increase the amount of propogated errors.

Increasing number of observations affects the quality of results. When, the number of observations increases the number of redundant increase. This directly affect the results it might reduce the amount of propogated error especially when having a precise

measurement. In addition, increasing number of observations will lead to enhance the geometry of measurements which increases accuracy and precision. This difference is illustrated in figures 27 and 28.

Figure 27, Comparison between numbers of observation of the easting misclosures

Figure 28, Comparison between numbers of observation of the easting misclosures

In general, with increasing the number of observations the quality of results has increased in both case easting and northing. This might be affected by increasing redundant and it might be affected by the enhanced geometry of angular measurements. Sometimes increasing the number of observations leads to reduce the propagated errors due to by chance accurate measurements.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECCOMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusions

In the theoretical study for any engineering surveying work the rate of propagated errors should not be out of range $\pm 3\sigma$. In this piece of work all the data were observed are in the high level of quality which all the data are in the confident level which is in the $\pm\sigma$ and $\pm 2\sigma$. This indicates that the data is precise and accurate. Outcomes of this dissertation are concluded;

1. The geometry of measurements affects the quality of the results which is tested in this study. The good geometry of angular measurements with in $> 30^\circ$ provides a more accurate and precise result than within $< 30^\circ$ angular measurements.
2. Moreover, the number of observations affects the quality of measurements. In the current dissertation the four, five, and six observations have been tested. The more number of observations provide the more accurate and precise results.
3. The different mathematical and algorithm of calculation provided different results. In this dissertation, the two different methods were used; Collins point method and least square method which they provided different qualified results with considering the different parameters for each of them.
4. There are 20 misclosures for both easting and northing coordinates from least square calculation. As a result, 19 out of 20 misclosures are in range $\pm\sigma$ it represents %95 of samples. Moreover, 1 out of 20 misclosures in range $\pm 2\sigma$ which is equivalent to %5 of samples.
5. The quality of results was affected by instruments' types. A few generations were proposed to this piece of work, after testing their precision and accuracy the decision was made to use TS60 which has a high precision and accuracy down to sub-millimetres.
6. The resection cab be used as a traverse or in the traverse adjustment can have resected control points, when the standard error is within the confident level.

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the derives results in chapter five, it is recommended that the researchers and surveyors could consider the following recommendations;

1. In this research project the five main control points were used, for the further work and research it is recommended to use the variety of control stations with different distances.
2. This thesis considered only four, five, and six observations, for the further work it might be better to investigate more observations to obtain more clear idea about number of measurements.
3. Surveyors and researchers can use all the proved mathematical method for their calculation, but it is better to use these methods has more redundant.
4. Investigators in this field should use or investigate the variety of geometry especially in angular measurements.
5. The surveyors can use resected point in traverse adjustments and the can use resected points as main control points in any survey control networks.

REFERENCES

- Allan, A. L., & Hollwey, J. R. (1968). Practical field surveying and computations (No. TA545 A45 1968).
- Anderson, J. M., Anderson, J. M., & Mikhail, E. M. (1998). Surveying, theory and practice. McGraw-Hill Science/Engineering/Math.
- Blachut, T. J., Chrzanowski, A., & Saastamoinen, J. H. (2012). Urban surveying and mapping. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Burtch, R. (2005). Three-point resection problem. Surveying computations course notes 2005/2006. Convention, Washington, D.C., September, pp 222-233.
- Hodges, D. J. and Smith, G. M. (1982). Underground survey: data in difficult conditions. in Conference of South African Surveyors, Johannesburg.
- Hodges, D. J., Nicholson, T. J. and Ketteman, M. R. (1984). Surface and underground automated mine surveys. The Mining Engineer, no. April, p. 465-470.
- Deakin, R. E. (1991). A review of least squares theory applied to traverse adjustment. Australian surveyor, 36(3), p.245-253.
- Deakin, R. E. (2006). Traverse computation on the UTM projection for surveys of limited extent.
- Deeth, C. (1984). Towards survey automation. Civil Engineering, 13.
- Directorate of Mineral Resources. (2010). Statistics for Fatal injuries, April to June 2010. Quarterly Newsletter of the Mine Health and Safety Inspectorate, October.
- Duggal, S. K. (2013). Surveying (Vol. 2). Tata McGraw-Hill Education.p.190-194.
- Faig, W. (1972). Advanced surveying, I:(preliminary copy) (Vol. 1). Dept. of Surveying Engineering, University of New Brunswick.
- Font-Llagunes, J. M., & Batlle, J. A. (2009). New method that solves the three-point resection problem using straight lines intersection. Journal of Surveying Engineering, 135(2), 39-45.
- Gary W. Fowler. (2015). Traverse Measurement. School of Natural Resources and Environment, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI 48109, U.S.A.
- Hazelton, B. (2008). HP-35s Calculator Program Crandall's Adjustment for a Closed Traverse.
- <https://www.google.co.uk/search?hl=en&authuser=0&site=imgphp&tbm=isch&source=hp&biw=&bih=&q=closed+traverse&btnG=Search+by+image#hl=en&authuser=0&tbm=isch&q=closed+traverse&imgsrc=qwP3eN1XY1TjeM%3A>. August 2016.
- Hu, W. C., & Kuang, J. S. (1998). Proof of Tienstra's formula for an external observation point. Journal of surveying engineering, 124(1), 49-55.

- ICSM. (2013). Standard for the Australian Survey Control Network – Special Publication 1, Version 2.0, Intergovernmental Committee on Surveying and Mapping, Canberra, Australia.
- Ryder, J. A. (2002). Rock Mechanics for tabular hard rock mines. The safety in mines research advisory committee (SIMRAC), Johannesburg.
- Pretorius, J. J. and Crous, J. E. (1967). Standard instructions for Mine Surveyors. Journal of the Institute of Mine surveyors of South Africa, vol. 14, no. 7, p. 209.
- Kissam, P. (1981). Surveying for civil engineers. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Papo, H., & Peled, A. (1977). Adjustment of A Traverse Network. Survey Review, 24(184), 82-92.
- Porta, J.M. and Thomas, F., 2009. Concise proof of Tienstra's formula. Journal of Surveying Engineering, 135(4), pp.170-172.
- Bannister, R. S. B. R. A. (1998). Surveying. 7th Edition, Pearson Education Limited, ISBN 0-582-30249-8.
- Šiaudinytė, L., & Suh, H. S. (2015). Uncertainty evaluation of proposed setup for the calibration of vertical angle measuring systems by using means for the flat angle calibration. Measurement, 67, p.177-182.
- Song, Z., Zhao, C., Pu, H., & Li, X. (2016). Configuration Analysis of Two-Dimensional Resection Networks. Journal of Surveying Engineering, 04016018.
- Sprinsky, W. H. (1987). Transverse adjustment for observations from modern survey instrumentation. Journal of surveying engineering, 113(2), p.70-81.
- Thornton-Smith, G. J. (1949). A modification of Bowditch's rule, to preserve the bearing of the datum line in a closed traverse. Empire Survey Review, 10(73), 111-119.
- Ziemann, H., (1974). Terrestrial Surveying Methods. Proceedings of ACSM Fall

APPENDICES

1: Measured Data

A. Four Observation Measured Data

Readings from point A				
	Azimuths			Distances
Units	d	m	s	m
p1	165	34	20	52
p2	187	12	36	46
p3	202	12	0	44
p4	215	40	48	47
Readings from point B				
p5	146	21	54	34
p6	208	46	12	30
p7	231	19	48	36
p8	244	1	48	17
Readings from point C				
p9	25	0	21	20
p10	234	39	47	21
p11	311	56	14	39
p12	339	19	48	18
Readings from point D				
p13	19	47	24	37
p14	63	30	0	30
p15	338	48	0	27
p16	357	0	25	32
Readings from point E				
p17	114	37	19	13
p18	117	21	11	43
p19	126	6	22	56
p20	129	23	13	25

Table 1, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 1 with four observations.

From point B						
	Orientations			Directions		
units	d	m	s	d	m	s
p1	87	14	41	30	8	45
p2	80	2	10	22	56	14
p3	69	32	49	12	26	53
p4	57	5	56	0	0	0
From point C						
p5	42	20	7	0	0	0
p6	62	38	22	20	18	15
p7	74	27	36	32	7	29
p8	51	45	6	9	24	59
From point D						
p9	59	20	1	0	0	0
p10	98	40	23	39	20	22
p11	135	0	42	75	40	41

p12	86	6	30	26	46	29
From point E						
p13	96	53	21	30	22	28
p14	66	30	53	0	0	0
p15	86	39	10	20	8	17
p16	92	16	0	25	45	7
From point A						
p17	58	49	10	0	0	0
p18	90	0	55	31	10	45
p19	111	37	29	52	48	19
p20	59	58	30	1	9	20

Table 2, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 1 with four observations.

Readings from point A				
units	Azimuths			Distances
	d	m	s	m
p1	100	16	54	53.151
p2	127	27	42	37.76
p3	138	5	31	33.143
p4	165	28	46	36.007
Readings from point B				
p5	111	37	24	26.736
p6	129	48	18	43.914
p7	149	2	21	35.902
p8	194	24	37	17.715
Readings from point C				
p9	246	1	48	41.032
p10	256	36	42	55.226
p11	273	28	25	41.456
p12	287	42	14	23.276
Readings from point D				
p13	58	42	16	26.494
p14	280	25	54	32.947
p15	311	35	8	57.28
p16	358	24	35	39.135
Readings from point E				
p17	4	39	43	28.612
p18	48	9	49	47.519
p19	76	44	36	27.187
p20	326	23	40	35.775

Table 3, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 2 with four observations.

From point B						
units	Orientations			Directions		
	d	m	s	d	m	s
p1	33	32	8	31	20	42
p2	22	35	4	20	23	38
p3	15	39	27	13	28	1
p4	2	11	26	0	0	0
From point C						

p5	38	50	45	24	49	34
p6	57	23	38	43	22	27
p7	49	33	56	35	32	45
p8	14	1	11	0	0	0
From point D						
p9	147	10	38	32	5	16
p10	163	1	22	47	56	0
p11	135	29	43	20	24	21
p12	115	5	22	0	0	0
From point E						
p13	65	28	56	0	0	0
p14	122	44	49	57	15	53
p15	154	34	59	89	6	3
p16	98	22	41	32	53	45
From point A						
p17	163	8	1	26	53	35
p18	153	48	18	17	33	52
p19	136	14	26	0	0	0
p20	167	49	3	31	34	37

Table 4, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 2 with four observations.

Readings from point A				
units	Azimuths			Distances
	d	m	s	m
p1	102	49	12	53.175
p2	133	46	45	42.701
p3	144	1	54	26.931
p4	172	11	22	35.259
Readings from point B				
p5	85	24	39	37.74
p6	101	58	48	42.154
p7	125	21	6	47.657
p8	164	28	21	24.621
Readings from point C				
p9	243	59	50	45.135
p10	264	7	47	32.501
p11	300	47	58	30.622
p12	321	34	17	32.973
Readings from point D				
p13	13	15	2	20.576
p14	253	0	16	40.072
p15	299	30	0	21.893
p16	344	16	57	17.69
Readings from point E				
p17	6	18	10	27.852
p18	64	2	54	35.497
p19	83	57	58	44.088
p20	329	5	15	47.123

Table 5, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 3 with four observations.

From point B						
	Orientations			Directions		
units	d	m	s	d	m	s
p1	120	46	39	43	6	52
p2	110	17	18	32	37	31
p3	92	12	48	14	33	1
p4	77	39	47	0	0	0
From point C						
p5	39	43	18	9	56	23
p6	47	49	50	18	2	55
p7	59	43	57	29	57	2
p8	29	46	55	0	0	0
From point D						
p9	73	6	4	59	46	17
p10	56	49	23	43	29	44
p11	31	27	28	18	7	41
p12	13	19	47	0	0	0
From point E						
p13	51	8	53	0	0	0
p14	104	32	30	53	23	37
p15	86	30	44	35	21	51
p16	64	45	50	13	36	57
From point A						
p17	75	57	34	36	48	13
p18	56	6	25	16	57	4
p19	39	9	21	0	0	0
p20	86	39	34	47	30	13

Table 6, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 3 with four observations.

Readings from point A				
	Azimuths			Distances
units	d	m	s	m
p1	115	29	40	37.103
p2	134	39	20	30.784
p3	147	19	4	35.072
p4	162	33	33	33.521
Readings from point B				
p5	94	41	22	37.369
p6	159	53	39	30.136
p7	185	40	19	25.655
p8	212	55	57	26.766
Readings from point C				
p9	283	44	20	38.222
p10	296	12	16	33.461
p11	316	34	56	38.657
p12	335	47	46	30.515
Readings from point D				
p13	46	15	17	38.16
p14	24	57	40	33.18
p15	351	54	3	24.91
p16	327	43	46	33.828

Readings from point E				
p17	49	47	55	30.916
p18	64	5	47	36.16
p19	77	21	21	44.029
p20	97	22	47	34.29

Table 7, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 4 with four observations.

From point B						
units	Orientations			Directions		
	d	m	s	d	m	s
p1	104	6	24	24	24	35
p2	93	50	8	14	8	19
p3	90	53	46	11	11	57
p4	79	41	49	0	0	0
From point C						
p5	55	42	17	13	56	1
p6	60	20	50	18	34	34
p7	52	6	29	10	20	13
p8	41	46	16	0	0	0
From point D						
p9	56	33	1	38	57	33
p10	43	35	46	26	0	18
p11	24	1	4	6	25	36
p12	17	35	28	0	0	0
From point E						
p13	49	13	28	0	0	0
p14	60	45	45	11	32	17
p15	87	33	37	38	20	9
p16	109	46	9	60	32	41
From point A						
p17	80	1	7	20	34	36
p18	75	10	1	15	43	30
p19	66	46	22	7	19	51
p20	59	26	31	0	0	0

Table 8, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 4 with four observations.

B. Five Observation Measured Data

Readings from point A				
	Azimuths			Distances
units	d	m	s	m
p1	119	8	44	42.522
p2	127	27	42	37.76
p3	138	5	31	33.143
p4	150	50	25	25.12
p5	165	28	46	36.007
Readings from point B				
p6	111	37	24	26.736
p7	129	48	18	43.914
p8	149	2	21	35.902
p9	170	36	23	25.643
p10	194	24	37	17.715
Readings from point C				
p11	246	1	48	41.032
p12	256	36	42	55.226
p13	265	50	18	34.612
p14	273	28	25	41.456
p15	287	42	14	23.276
Readings from point D				
p16	58	42	16	26.494
p17	280	25	54	32.947
p18	297	1	33	39.82
p19	311	35	8	57.28
p20	358	24	35	39.135
Readings from point E				
p21	4	39	43	28.612
p22	15	3	41	37.098
p23	33	31	30	31.36
p24	48	9	49	47.519
p25	76	44	36	27.187

Table 9, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 1 with five observations.

From point B						
	Orientations			Directions		
units	d	m	s	d	m	s
p1	27	45	1	25	33	35
p2	22	35	4	20	23	38
p3	15	39	27	13	28	1
p4	4	59	43	2	48	17
p5	2	11	26	0	0	0
From point C						
p6	38	50	45	24	49	34
p7	57	23	38	43	22	27
p8	49	33	56	35	32	45
p9	29	22	22	15	21	11
p10	14	1	11	0	0	0
From point D						
p11	147	10	38	32	5	16

p12	163	1	22	47	56	0
p13	133	41	39	18	36	17
p14	135	29	43	20	24	21
p15	115	5	22	0	0	0
From point E						
p16	78	7	47	12	38	51
p17	65	28	56	0	0	0
p18	122	44	49	57	15	53
p19	132	12	41	66	43	45
p20	154	34	59	89	6	3
From point A						
p21	167	31	40	31	17	14
p22	156	42	37	20	28	11
p23	153	48	18	17	33	52
p24	136	14	26	0	0	0
p25	167	49	3	31	34	37

Table 10, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 1 with five observations.

Readings from point A				
units	Azimuths			Distances
	d	m	s	m
p1	117	7	18	46.166
p2	133	46	45	42.701
p3	144	1	54	26.931
p4	159	37	44	31.782
p5	172	11	22	35.259
Readings from point B				
p6	101	58	48	42.154
p7	110	32	59	42.58
p8	125	21	6	47.657
p9	135	13	50	31.623
p10	164	28	21	24.621
Readings from point C				
p11	243	59	50	45.135
p12	264	7	47	32.501
p13	280	12	40	33.591
p14	300	47	58	30.622
p15	321	34	17	32.973
Readings from point D				
p16	253	0	16	40.072
p17	268	45	37	32.41
p18	299	30	0	21.893
p19	321	17	3	20.864
p20	344	16	57	17.69
Readings from point E				
p21	6	18	10	27.852
p22	32	6	59	18.93
p23	64	2	54	35.497
p24	83	57	58	44.088
p25	329	5	15	47.123

Table 11, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 2 with five observations.

From point B						
units	Orientations			Directions		
	d	m	s	d	m	s
p1	116	33	0	38	53	13
p2	110	17	18	32	37	31
p3	92	12	48	14	33	1
p4	86	40	56	9	1	9
p5	77	39	47	0	0	0
From point C						
p6	47	49	50	18	2	55
p7	50	55	49	21	8	54
p8	59	43	57	29	57	2
p9	44	52	4	15	5	9
p10	29	46	55	0	0	0
From point D						
p11	73	6	4	59	46	17
p12	56	49	23	43	29	44
p13	49	56	26	36	36	39
p14	31	27	28	18	7	41
p15	13	19	47	0	0	0
From point E						
p16	51	8	53	0	0	0
p17	104	32	30	53	23	37
p18	101	25	22	50	16	29
p19	86	30	44	35	21	51
p20	76	46	35	25	37	42
From point A						
p21	65	52	33	26	43	12
p22	56	6	25	16	57	4
p23	39	9	21	0	0	0
p24	86	39	34	47	30	13
p25	82	56	4	43	46	43

Table 12, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 2 with five observations.

Readings from point A				
units	Azimuths			Distances
	d	m	s	m
p1	97	46	50	46.995
p2	115	29	40	37.103
p3	134	39	20	30.784
p4	147	19	4	35.072
p5	162	33	33	33.521
Readings from point B				
p6	115	47	12	46.019
p7	152	17	51	44.036
p8	159	53	39	30.136
p9	185	40	19	25.655

p10	212	55	57	26.766
Readings from point C				
p11	260	44	45	53.013
p12	283	44	20	38.222
p13	296	12	16	33.461
p14	316	34	56	38.657
p15	335	47	46	30.515
Readings from point D				
p16	24	57	40	33.18
p17	351	54	3	24.91
p18	327	43	46	33.828
p19	316	9	49	40.678
p20	308	42	46	50.019
Readings from point E				
p21	10	41	58	34.378
p22	32	36	36	47.999
p23	49	47	55	30.916
p24	64	5	47	36.16
p25	77	21	21	44.029

Table 13, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 3 with five observations.

From point B						
units	Orientations			Directions		
	d	m	s	d	m	s
p1	111	55	41	32	13	52
p2	104	6	24	24	24	35
p3	93	50	8	14	8	19
p4	90	53	46	11	11	57
p5	79	41	49	0	0	0
From point C						
p6	64	56	55	23	10	39
p7	71	16	32	29	30	16
p8	60	20	50	18	34	34
p9	52	6	29	10	20	13
p10	41	46	16	0	0	0
From point D						
p11	82	13	5	64	37	37
p12	56	33	1	38	57	33
p13	43	35	46	26	0	18
p14	24	1	4	6	25	36
p15	17	35	28	0	0	0
From point E						
p16	49	13	28	0	0	0
p17	60	45	45	11	32	17
p18	87	33	37	38	20	9
p19	109	46	9	60	32	41
p20	123	14	54	74	1	26
From point A						
p21	95	59	30	36	32	59
p22	80	1	7	20	34	36
p23	75	10	1	15	43	30
p24	66	46	22	7	19	51

p25	59	26	31	0	0	0
-----	----	----	----	---	---	---

Table 14, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 3 with five observations.

C. Six Observation Measured Data

Readings from point A				
units	Azimuths			Distances
	d	m	s	m
p1	100	16	54	53.151
p2	119	8	44	42.522
p3	127	27	42	37.76
p4	138	5	31	33.143
p5	150	50	25	25.12
p6	165	28	46	36.007
Readings from point B				
p7	99	36	8	39.085
p8	111	37	24	26.736
p9	129	48	18	43.914
p10	149	2	21	35.902
p11	170	36	23	25.643
p12	194	24	37	17.715
Readings from point C				
p13	232	2	19	46.685
p14	246	1	48	41.032
p15	256	36	42	55.226
p16	265	50	18	34.612
p17	273	28	25	41.456
p18	287	42	14	23.276
Readings from point D				
p19	24	3	48	23.914
p20	58	42	16	26.494
p21	280	25	54	32.947
p22	297	1	33	39.82
p23	311	35	8	57.28
p24	358	24	35	39.135
Readings from point E				
p25	4	39	43	28.612
p26	15	3	41	37.098
p27	33	31	30	31.36
p28	48	9	49	47.519
p29	76	44	36	27.187
p30	326	23	40	35.775

Table 15, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 1 with six observations.

From point B						
units	Orientations			Directions		
	d	m	s	d	m	s
p1	33	32	8	31	20	42
p2	27	45	1	25	33	35
p3	22	35	4	20	23	38

p4	15	39	27	13	28	1
p5	4	59	43	2	48	17
p6	2	11	26	0	0	0
From point C						
p7	45	23	53	31	22	42
p8	38	50	45	24	49	34
p9	57	23	38	43	22	27
p10	49	33	56	35	32	45
p11	29	22	22	15	21	11
p12	14	1	11	0	0	0
From point D						
p13	152	33	37	37	28	15
p14	147	10	38	32	5	16
p15	163	1	22	47	56	0
p16	133	41	39	18	36	17
p17	135	29	43	20	24	21
p18	115	5	22	0	0	0
From point E						
p19	78	7	47	12	38	51
p20	65	28	56	0	0	0
p21	122	44	49	57	15	53
p22	132	12	41	66	43	45
p23	154	34	59	89	6	3
p24	98	22	41	32	53	45
From point A						
p25	163	8	1	26	53	35
p26	167	31	40	31	17	14
p27	156	42	37	20	28	11
p28	153	48	18	17	33	52
p29	136	14	26	0	0	0
p30	167	49	3	31	34	37

Table 16, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 1 with six observations.

Readings from point A				
	Azimuths			Distances
units	d	m	s	m
p1	85	50	1	61
p2	97	46	50	47
p3	115	29	40	37.1
p4	134	39	20	30.8
p5	147	19	4	35.1
p6	162	33	33	33.5
Readings from point B				
p7	94	41	22	37.4
p8	115	47	12	46
p9	152	17	51	44
p10	159	53	39	30.1
p11	185	40	19	25.7
p12	212	55	57	26.8
Readings from point C				
p13	245	3	50	42.1
p14	260	44	45	53

p15	283	44	20	38.2
p16	296	12	16	33.5
p17	316	34	56	38.7
p18	335	47	46	30.5
Readings from point D				
p19	46	15	17	38.2
p20	24	57	40	33.2
p21	351	54	3	24.9
p22	327	43	46	33.8
p23	316	9	49	40.7
p24	308	42	46	50
Readings from point E				
p25	10	41	58	34.4
p26	32	36	36	48
p27	49	47	55	30.9
p28	64	5	47	36.2
p29	77	21	21	44
p30	97	22	47	34.3

Table 17, Observations for establishing minor control points, trial 3 with six observations.

From point B						
units	Orientations			Directions		
	d	m	s	d	m	s
p1	117	42	26	38	0	37
p2	111	55	41	32	13	52
p3	104	6	24	24	24	35
p4	93	50	8	14	8	19
p5	90	53	46	11	11	57
p6	79	41	49	0	0	0
From point C						
p7	55	42	17	13	56	1
p8	64	56	55	23	10	39
p9	71	16	32	29	30	16
p10	60	20	50	18	34	34
p11	52	6	29	10	20	13
p12	41	46	16	0	0	0
From point D						
p13	70	41	58	53	6	30
p14	82	13	5	64	37	37
p15	56	33	1	38	57	33
p16	43	35	46	26	0	18
p17	24	1	4	6	25	36
p18	17	35	28	0	0	0
From point E						
p19	49	13	28	0	0	0
p20	60	45	45	11	32	17
p21	87	33	37	38	20	9
p22	109	46	9	60	32	41
p23	123	14	54	74	1	26
p24	135	37	24	86	23	56
From point A						
p25	90	31	50	31	5	19
p26	95	59	30	36	32	59

p27	80	1	7	20	34	36
p28	75	10	1	15	43	30
p29	66	46	22	7	19	51
p30	59	26	31	0	0	0

Table 18, Observations from resected points to establish main control points, trial 3 with six observations.